

Reimagining Nikola Tesla in Video Games: Aesthetic Reinvention and Narrative Manipulation

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From Historical Figure to Playable Myth: Nikola Tesla in Video Game Culture

The inclusion of historical figures in the narratives and plots of video games has become increasingly common. Characters such as Cleopatra, Julius Caesar, Genghis Khan, Mahatma Gandhi, Leonardo da Vinci, and Winston Churchill, among many others, have appeared in numerous video games, often portrayed in ways that distance them from their historical context. It is precisely this departure from the image traditionally projected by history that creates a sharp tension between the social imaginary associated with these figures and the new aesthetic and narrative representations constructed by video games. In response, this study seeks to identify the dissonances between historical representation and contemporary reinterpretation, to detect the aesthetic and narrative manipulations present in video games, and to relate these changes to the specific characteristics of the medium, which combines interactive characters with subjective player experiences. To do so, the chapter focuses on the representation of Nikola Tesla, one of the most recurrent historical figures in the video game industry. The study adapts methods of audiovisual character analysis and theories of video game narrative construction in order to examine the fourteen games in which the inventor of alternating current appears either as a protagonist or as a secondary character. The results suggest that Tesla's image has been manipulated primarily at the narrative level, and to a lesser extent at the aesthetic level. Video games frequently reproduce an antiheroic version of Tesla, portraying him as a savior of humanity, exaggerating his rivalry with Thomas Edison, and presenting him in ways that are often diametrically opposed to his historical representation. This phenomenon, which can also be extended to other historical figures, creates a schism between the social imaginary and the historical substratum, as video games project new instrumentalized images of historical characters.

Between History and Fiction: Narrative, Intertextuality, and the Digital Reinvention of Historical Figures

In the same way that historical novels and films based on real events have traditionally done, the video game industry often draws upon historical moments to construct the settings in which its stories unfold, as well as the plots, subplots, and tragedies that drive its protagonists' narrative engines (Cuadrado-Alvarado, 2020). Specific periods such as the Middle Ages or the Renaissance, along with key episodes in history such as the French Revolution or the Industrial Revolution, frequently form part of the narrative background of video games that seek either to represent part of human history or simply to situate their stories within a recognizable historical context.

This is particularly common in war and historical games, in which players are able to relive specific moments of conflict and combat, such as the Normandy landings in *Medal of Honor: Allied Assault* or *Call of Duty: WWII*. Although many of these games attempt to portray warfare realistically, scholars such as Moreno and Venegas argue that video games are “an unreliable source for learning about war firsthand” (2020, p. 16). However, some video games go beyond the mere recreation of historical settings by representing real historical figures from multiple perspectives, including some that are highly unrealistic and closer to fantasy than historical reconstruction. For example, it is possible to see Mahatma Gandhi leading Indian military forces in a campaign to conquer the world in *Sid Meier's Civilization V*, or Leonardo da Vinci designing inventions to assist the Assassin Brotherhood in its centuries-long struggle against the Templars in *Assassin's Creed II*.

Likewise, Adolf Hitler frequently appears as the main villain in several installments of the *Wolfenstein* franchise, which imagines a dystopian scenario in which the World War II ended in victory for the Third Reich. Another common example is the representation of the gangster Al Capone in video games centered on the Italian mafia, such as *Empire of Sin*, where he appears as a playable character, or *Blues and Bullets*, which imagines an alternative story involving Capone and Eliot Ness. In these cases, the representation of Italians or Italian Americans in mafia-related video games contributes to the reproduction of racial stereotypes within the gaming sector as well (Pitrosso, 2019).

Other long-running and popular franchises in digital entertainment make use of the images of historical figures such as Cleopatra, Julius Caesar, Genghis Khan, Winston Churchill, or Stephen Hawking under parameters that distance them from their original historical contexts. It is precisely this distance from the image traditionally projected by history that generates a sharp clash between the social imaginary associated with

these figures and the new aesthetic and narrative representation that the medium projects onto society.

Accordingly, this study seeks to identify the dissonances between historical representation and the new image created by video games, to detect the aesthetic and narrative manipulations present in the medium, and finally to establish the common characteristics and variables found across different works that shape this new imaginary. To do so, the chapter focuses on the representation of Nikola Tesla, one of the historical figures with the greatest presence in the video game industry over the last two decades, coinciding with the resurgence of the Croatian scientist as a mass-media icon and symbol of popular culture.

In addition to being one of the most recurrent historical figures in gaming, Tesla's representation also makes it possible to open discussions about scientific discourse and scientific education within the medium, which, as Balada and Bovolenta (2022, p. 3) note, "is directly linked to the construction of approaches from the perspective of scientific and technological literacy that considers its social function." Just as some scholars have studied the realism of particular franchises (Cuartero, 2018), others have analyzed the reproduction of historical racial stereotypes (Pitrosso, 2019) or the interpretation of locations in video games (Venegas, 2018). This study instead proposes to analyze the representation of a specific historical figure within the medium.

Consequently, the main research objectives are to identify the dissonances between historical representation and contemporary reinterpretation, to detect the aesthetic and narrative manipulations present in digital media, and finally to relate them to the specific characteristics of video games, which incorporate the interactive and subjective figure of the player. Ultimately, the study seeks to discuss how the fictional representation of a scientist may affect the perception of the character, the construction of identity, and the broader social imaginary surrounding science and scientific discourse.

Tracking Tesla Across Games: A Comparative Analysis of Historical Representation

Based on these premises, the main research questions guiding this study are as follows: Is there aesthetic and narrative manipulation in the representation of Nikola Tesla in video games? If so, what kind of figure is Tesla portrayed as, and which identifying traits and characteristics shape his personal image?

To address these questions, it was first necessary to conduct an exhaustive search within the video game industry in order to identify all titles featuring representations of Tesla. This search focused on

mainstream games and was based on a combination of two of the largest international video game databases: IGDB and GameFAQs. These databases allow users to search for works by genre, release year, platform, and format, including PC games, mobile games, virtual reality titles, and others. The final search yielded a total of fourteen video games that include different forms of representation of Tesla as a scientist and inventor. The search covered all games released up to and including April 2023.

The following table summarizes the inclusion criteria used in the video-documentary search conducted through the IGDB and GameFAQs databases:

Variable	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Type	Mainstream commercial video games	Illegal or unreleased games
Nationality	All	—
Genre	All	—
Year of publication	Up to and including April 2023	—
Platforms	All	—
Types of representation	Protagonist, secondary character, or antagonist, regardless of whether the character is playable	Cases where the representation is merely anecdotal, such as a passing mention. For example, in <i>BioShock Infinite</i> a means of transport is named “Tesla.” Such references were not considered significant.

Through this mixed-method approach (Campos, 2021), which combines qualitative and quantitative analysis, and considering the cultural value of video games—which, like cinema or literature, can be understood as creators of cultural and social imaginaries (Aldegani, 2022) and as media capable of expanding narratives through intertextual elements (Freire et al., 2022)—the results and comparative analysis make it possible to understand how Tesla is represented across all titles in which

he appears, whether as a main character, secondary figure, antagonist, or allegorical presence.

The Scientist, the Hero, and the Myth: Reimagining Tesla in Video Games

A total of fourteen video games featuring the figure of Nikola Tesla were identified. These titles were organized chronologically, including information on developer, year of release, and genre. As the sample shows, the games span from 2008 to 2022. The most common genre is action, although this is not particularly significant, since Tesla appears across a wide range of genres, including strategy, adventure and open-world games, platform games, shooters, fighting games, and interactive fiction.

With the exception of *Assassin's Creed Syndicate*, *The Order: 1886*, and *Red Dead Redemption 2*, most of the titles are indie productions developed by small or medium-sized studios. The earliest title in the sample, *Tesla Wars*, was originally designed for mobile devices and uses Tesla's inventions and theories to construct an apocalyptic world in which players must build electric towers to defend themselves against enemy invasions. In this game, Tesla's presence is largely allegorical, and—as in many of the analyzed titles—his scientific achievements are repurposed toward warfare and military progress.

Dark Void was the first game to portray Tesla as a mentor or secondary character who assists the protagonist through his scientific expertise and ability to create inventions and weapons. In this case, Tesla equips the main characters with jetpacks that allow them to fly. However, his representation, particularly in terms of personality, departs significantly from the historical record.

Tesla: The Weather Man is the first title to use Tesla as the main protagonist and playable character. In a somewhat caricatured version of the inventor, Tesla uses his inventions to control the weather and wield lightning in his struggle against a surreal version of Thomas Edison, who seeks to dominate the world through an army of automatons.

Two years later, *Teslagrad* was released. Although Tesla himself does not appear as a character, the game pays tribute to many of his inventions and scientific breakthroughs. Its central setting, the Tesla Tower, is built around puzzles, traps, and electrical mechanisms inspired by his legacy. *Tesla Breaks the World!* again presents Tesla as

a playable protagonist. Once more, he assumes the role of a hero who must save the world from the threat posed by Edison, here depicted as a mad scientist commanding an army of zombies. This title, like *Tesla: The Weather Man*, exaggerates the historical conflict between Tesla and Edison, portraying Tesla as a heroic figure who uses technology to save humanity, while Edison becomes a stereotypical villain. In *Assassin's Creed Syndicate*, Tesla appears as a non-playable secondary character who helps the protagonists, Jacob and Evie Frye, in their struggle against the Templars. Ubisoft's version depicts Tesla as a brilliant and eccentric inventor, but also as a scientist deeply concerned with humanity. This is one of the first games to create a character who is aesthetically close to the real Tesla.

Similarly, *The Order: 1886* represents Tesla as a young scientific genius who develops advanced weapons for an order fighting werewolves and other supernatural creatures. In this game, Tesla once again occupies the role of the inventor who supports the protagonist through technology. *Science Combat* exaggerates the rivalry between Tesla and Edison even further by turning it into a fighting game in which famous scientists—including Marie Curie, Albert Einstein, and Charles Darwin—battle one another with superhuman powers. This Brazilian title caricatures all of its scientists and disregards both their historical contexts and personalities. *The Invisible Hours* portrays Tesla as an eccentric and egotistical inventor who invites a group of famous guests—including Edison—to his mansion on a remote island, only to be murdered shortly afterward. Inspired by the detective fiction of Agatha Christie, the game uses Tesla as the catalyst for a murder mystery narrative.

In *Tesla vs Lovecraft* and *Tesla Force*, Tesla is once again portrayed as an action hero, battling monsters inspired by the works of H. P. Lovecraft. Armed with electrical weapons, teleportation devices, and advanced gadgets, Tesla becomes a larger-than-life heroic figure capable of fighting armies of supernatural creatures.

Red Dead Redemption 2 includes a character named Marko Dragic, a fictionalized parody of Tesla who shares certain visual similarities with the scientist. True to the satirical style often employed by Rockstar Games, Dragic is represented as an even more eccentric and extravagant version of Tesla, bordering on charlatanry.

Finally, both *Close to the Sun* and *Nikola Tesla: War of the Currents* present alternative realities in which Tesla made different choices in life and ultimately succeeded in bringing electricity to the

entire world. However, while *Close to the Sun* imagines a dystopian society created by Tesla's ambitions, *Nikola Tesla: War of the Currents* focuses on strategic decision-making and alternative historical scenarios.

Overall, the findings reveal several recurring patterns. In 100% of the games analyzed, Tesla is represented primarily as a scientist. However, in 71% of the titles, his scientific work is linked to warfare, combat, or military applications, which differs significantly from his real-life goals. Tesla appears as a protagonist in 36% of the sample, usually in the role of hero and occasionally as an antihero. In another 36%, he is portrayed as a secondary character, while in 29% of the cases his presence is allegorical rather than personified.

Tesla is never directly represented as a villain, although *Close to the Sun* positions him as indirectly responsible for a dystopian society. When he appears as a secondary character, he usually embodies the stereotype of the inventor who assists the hero by providing weapons, gadgets, or technological expertise.

In terms of narrative background, 78% of the games construct a fantastic or fictionalized biography, while only 14% use real events but alter part of Tesla's story—particularly his rivalry with Edison during the so-called “War of the Currents.” Nearly half of the games portray Edison as Tesla's principal antagonist, while two games replace Edison with Lovecraftian enemies.

From an aesthetic perspective, the dominant visual style is steampunk, which combines Victorian imagery with futuristic technology and mechanical inventions. Around 43% of the games exaggerate or caricature Tesla's appearance and personality, while only a minority attempt to represent him realistically.

Finally, the two traits that most closely align with the historical record are Tesla's obsessive personality and his altruistic interest in science. However, most of the games also assign him traits that are inconsistent with his biography, particularly portraying him as bellicose, violent, or militaristic.

Tesla as an Antiheroic Figure in Video Games

The findings of this study can also be interpreted through the lens of the antihero and antiheroine framework proposed by Freire and Vidal-Mestre (2022). According to these authors, antiheroes differ from traditional heroes because they are imperfect, morally ambiguous, emotionally unstable, and often marked by trauma, obsession, or social

alienation. Rather than embodying virtue in the classical sense, antiheroes are defined by their flaws, internal contradictions, and their distance from institutional power or dominant norms.

In the case of Nikola Tesla, video games rarely portray him as a conventional heroic scientist. Instead, they frequently construct him as a character who combines brilliance with eccentricity, obsession, social isolation, and a certain disregard for moral or political limits. These traits align Tesla with the contemporary antiheroic archetype identified by Freire and Vidal-Mestre, particularly in games such as *Close to the Sun*, *The Invisible Hours*, or *Tesla vs Lovecraft*, where he appears as a misunderstood genius, consumed by his work and often detached from ordinary human relationships.

This antiheroic representation is especially visible in the recurring emphasis on Tesla's obsessive personality, his rivalry with Thomas Edison, and his willingness to use science in violent or morally ambiguous ways. Rather than presenting him as a purely benevolent inventor, these games frame him as a figure suspended between altruism and danger, capable of saving humanity but also of causing destruction. In this sense, Tesla embodies one of the most recurrent features of contemporary antiheroes: the coexistence of admirable intentions and questionable methods.

Moreover, Freire and Vidal-Mestre argue that antiheroes are particularly successful in transmedia culture because they are more human, relatable, and psychologically complex than traditional heroes. Tesla's representation in video games follows this trend: his image as an isolated, eccentric, and unfairly treated genius makes him emotionally compelling for contemporary audiences, especially younger players who tend to connect more strongly with flawed and misunderstood characters than with idealized heroic models. Therefore, beyond the aesthetic and narrative manipulation identified throughout this study, the representation of Tesla in video games can also be understood as part of a broader cultural movement toward antiheroic protagonists. Rather than reproducing the image of the scientist as a detached intellectual or a stereotypical mad genius, video games reconfigure Tesla as a conflicted, emotionally complex, and antiheroic figure adapted to the narrative sensibilities of contemporary popular culture.

Playing with History: Tesla, Popular Culture, and the Transformation of Historical Memory

The study demonstrates that, much like film and television, video games are products of their time, reflecting the dominant interests, concerns, and cultural trends of a given historical moment. In recent years, Nikola Tesla has become a figure of popular culture in much the same way as Albert Einstein or Stephen Hawking. The emergence of games centered on Tesla—or those that use him as a secondary or allegorical character—coincides with the broader resurgence of Tesla as a pop-cultural icon. This renewed visibility is directly linked to the influence of novels, biographies, and films that emphasize the mysticism of Tesla’s life and his struggle against adversity, including illness, financial hardship, professional discredit, and the appropriation of his inventions. Among the works that contributed most to this renewed interest are *The Prestige*, in which David Bowie portrays Tesla, and the biography *Nikola Tesla: El genio al que le robaron la luz* by Margaret Cheney.

As a result, Tesla has gone from relative obscurity to becoming a protagonist, secondary character, or symbolic presence in numerous games, including some of the most successful franchises in the history of the medium, such as *Red Dead Redemption 2* and *Assassin's Creed Syndicate*. It is therefore possible to argue that, as long as Tesla remains an icon because of both his technological legacy and the injustices he suffered, his life and work will continue to be represented in video games. In this sense, Tesla’s famous phrase—“the future is mine”—appears especially fitting.

Another important finding concerns the representation of Tesla as a scientist. Both cinema and video games have often portrayed scientists as obsessive figures, consumed by their work and potentially dangerous because of their inventions. In some cases, scientists are even associated with stereotypical villains who use scientific progress for domination and destruction. However, the portrayal of Tesla in video games tends instead toward the heroic or antiheroic. When he appears as a protagonist, he is usually represented as a heroic inventor fighting to save humanity; when he appears as a secondary character, he is often depicted as a brilliant ally who helps the protagonist through his scientific expertise.

In general, Tesla is portrayed as an eccentric, gifted, and heroic inventor. This representation therefore challenges some of the traditional stigmas attached to scientists in the cultural imaginary and may also contribute positively to the popularization of science.

At the same time, video games have significantly reshaped the public images of both Tesla and Thomas Edison. While the history of science long failed to fully recognize Tesla’s contributions, video games

emphasize the importance of his legacy while simultaneously intensifying his historical rivalry with Edison.

Titles such as *Tesla: The Weather Man*, *Tesla Breaks the World!*, and *Assassin's Creed Syndicate* depict Edison as a dangerous scientist, conspirator, and would-be dictator obsessed with power and global domination. By demonizing Edison and portraying him as a tyrannical and manipulative figure, these games contribute to reshaping—and in some cases damaging—his public image and scientific legacy.

This finding highlights the power of video games, much like cinema, to influence the public perception of historical figures and, more broadly, the public understanding of history itself.

Although both aesthetic and narrative manipulation are clearly present in the representation of Tesla and his biography, some games have also helped bring scientific discourse and Tesla's work closer to younger generations. They have contributed to making Tesla a symbol of resilience, injustice, and perseverance in the face of adversity, including the theft of patents and recognition. For this reason, Tesla's representation in video games should be understood as an artistic interpretation, a cultural manifestation of fantasy, and an audiovisual construction designed primarily for entertainment. Like science fiction films and novels before them, video games combine elements of reality with fictional invention.

Consequently, although games distort parts of Tesla's biography, they generally do so from a romanticized perspective. Players should therefore approach the representation of historical figures in video games with a critical distance—whether these figures are repositioned as heroic saviors of humanity, as in Tesla's case, or as deranged villains bent on world domination, as in Edison's.

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